

Table 1: Suggestions to implement ethical requirements and principles

Suggestions and Recommendations	References
Gaps identified and solutions provided: the lack of appropriate tools and standards, the absence of practical courses, the improper implementation of solutions, human bias, the lack of diversity within the AI community, the complexity of decisions, problems with industry funding and the lack of evaluation metrics.	[1]
The practical results include the utilisation of ethics-by-design procedures, constraints and models to facilitate the translation of ethical requirements into operational terms, and the usage of DfV to help with these tasks.	[2]
Infrastructure consisting of algorithms, tools and frameworks to address the broad scope of ethical requirements	[3]
Obstacles to the implementation: a lack of commitment to doing good exhibited by companies, lack of tradition in terms of being a good developer, lack of methods for translating principles into practice and lack of robust accountability mechanisms	[4]
Review of frameworks	[5]
Cascade method for the implementation of ethical requirements in organisations	[6]
Software Engineering Roadmap for RAI	[7]
A comprehensive field guide to the development of machine learning	[8]
Iterative method for the application of AI ethics	[9]
Ethical framework for designing AI systems	[10]
Set of good practices: model explainability components towards stakeholders, use a template for explainability requirements, organisation of workshops, understand the process supported by the system, define the system clearly for stakeholders and consider possible risks	[11]
Processes for implementing ethical principles and requirements	[12]

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